

PECULIARITIES OF ADJECTIVES IN FRENCH LANGUAGE

Nilufar Juraeva

Assistant professor, PhD
French Philology Department
Bukhara State University

n.s.juraeva@buxdu.uz

<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3116-4676>

Khazratova Farangiz

Student of Bukhara State University

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Annotation: An adjective is a word that describes a noun or pronoun. Adjective expresses the quality, characteristic, or feature of a thing, object, or person. Adjectives are an important part of speech in any language, including French. This article discusses the specific features of adjectives in French language.

Keywords: adjective, quality, noun, pronoun, masculine, feminine, singular, plural, size, shape, weight, color, nationality, types of adjectives, les adjectifs épithètes, les adjectifs attributs, formation, placement.

Introduction. Adjectives (les adjectifs) describe the qualities and characteristics of a noun, they describe how someone or something is. They always accompany the noun they describe, and the endings of an adjective always agree with the noun in terms of gender (masculine or feminine) and number (singular or plural).

Adjectives are a type of modifier, that is, they modify or describe nouns in a certain way, letting us know the size, shape, weight, color, nationality, or any of a myriad other possible qualities of nouns. Characteristics of French Adjectives:

- a) modify nouns;
- b) must agree in gender and number with nouns;
- c) usually follow nouns;
- d) may be modified by adverbs;
- e) gender and number of French adjectives.

French adjectives can have up to four forms, according to the gender and number of the nouns they modify:

masculine singular Masculine plural

feminine singular feminine plural

Examples:

le stylo bleu (masculine singular)

une femme gentille (feminine singular)

des jardins bien entretenus (masculine plural)

les rues françaises (feminine plural)

Main part. In this article, we will discuss the peculiarities of the adjectives in the French language.

Types of French adjectives. In French, there are two types of adjectives: *les adjectifs épithètes* and *les adjectifs attributs*.

L'adjectif épithète is an adjective that refers directly to a noun and usually comes after the noun it describes (although sometimes they come before). These adjectives cannot be separated by another word.

Examples:

Il faut aérer les pièces humides.

Regarde ce petit chat!

L'adjectif attribut also describes the qualities and characteristics of a noun, however it always appears together with a stative verb. The noun being described is the subject of the sentence and the adjective comes after the verb. The French stative verbs are: être, paraître, sembler, devenir, demeurer, rester, avoir l'air, passer pour. Examples:

Les élèves sont silencieux aujourd'hui.

Ce fauteuil a l'air confortable.

Formation. Generally, the feminine adjective is formed by adding an *e* and the plural adjective is formed by adding *s*:

Gender	Singular	Plural
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Masculine	intelligent	intelligents
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Feminine	intelligente	intelligentes
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If the masculine singular ends in *e*: do not change feminine, add an *s* for plural:

Gender	Singular	Plural
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Masculine	timide	timides
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Feminine	timide	timides
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If the masculine singular adjective ends in an *s*, add an *e* for feminine and *s* for feminine plural, but do not add an *s* for masculine plural:

Gender	Singular	Plural
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Masculine	français	français
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Gender Singular Plural

Feminine française françaises

Two other common changes occur with adjectives ending in *f* and *x*. If the masculine singular adjective ends in *f*, then it changes to *ve* in the feminine:

Gender Singular Plural

Masculine actif actifs

Feminine active actives

If the masculine singular adjective ends in *x*, then it changes to *se* in the feminine (but remains *x* in the masculine plural):

Gender Singular Plural

Masculine heureux heureux

Feminine heureuse heureuses

Placement. In French, most adjectives come after the noun, unlike in English where the adjective precedes the noun:

Un garçon intelligent / An intelligent boy

However, some adjectives are placed before the noun:

Un petit garçon / A small boy

The following are adjectives commonly placed before the noun:

French

English

Un beau livre.

A beautiful book.

Un bon professeur.

A good professor.

Un grand ordinateur.

A big computer.

Un gros dictionnaire.

A fat dictionary.

Une jeune fille.

A young girl.

Un mauvais étudiant.

A bad student

Un nouveau sac à dos. *A new backpack.*

Un petit garçon. *A small boy.*

Conclusion.

Adjectives are a part of speech that express the characteristics or features of a noun. An adjective primarily conveys the attribute of a subject or, to some extent, an action. The concept of an attribute includes features such as character, color, taste, shape, and size, among others. For example, in the phrases “green tree”, “big house”, “fast running”, the words “green”, “big” and “fast” function as adjectives. In French, adjectives agree in both number (singular or plural) and gender (masculine or feminine) with the noun or pronoun they modify. For regular adjectives, the masculine form is the base form to which endings are added.

A deeper study of the unique grammatical and semantic aspects of adjectives in French language helps to better understand their role and significance within the language systems.

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